

UV-C CABINET IMPLEMENTATION WORKSHEET

! This is a planning worksheet for facility implementation of a UV-C cabinet. This cabinet is not certified by any regulatory body and use must be approved by national, regional or facility authorities, according to the local context. Data on surgical mask decontamination via UV-C and impact on surgical mask performance are sparse - results on bioburden reduction are preliminary, internal, and unpublished. No warranties are implied and workflows are used at your own risk. PPE & hand hygiene best practices must be followed at all times.

N95DECON

OSA Foundation

BEFORE IMPLEMENTATION: HOSPITAL PLANNING

METHOD SELECTED:

A1 N95 Shortage/ Decon need

DESIGNATED DECON AREA:

PROTOCOL APPROVED BY:

A2 Designate space & protocol

N95 SUPPLY (TYPE/#):

SURGICAL MASK SUPPLY (TYPE/#):

A3 Catalog existing masks

REPROCESSING TEAM:

TRAINING PLAN:

A4 Select & train reprocessing staff

PREPARE NEW MASK*

B1 New N95 available?

RESPONSIBLE:

B2 Label mask

B3 Dons mask

B4 Clinical shift

REPROCESSING STAFF SHIFT BEGINS

F1 Staff enters area

F2 PPE available? Don PPE

F3 Staff handover

AFTER CLINICAL SHIFT: MASK DROPOFF

EVALUATED BY: LOGGED IN BY:

C1 Staff enters. Doff & Inspect mask

CONTAINER TYPE:

C2 Pack and label container

LOGGED IN BY:

C3 Log in mask

RESPONSIBLE:

C4 Load and transport for decon area

MASK REPROCESSING

RESPONSIBLE:

D1 Transport cart arrives/ unpack

VERIFIED BY:

D2 Load masks & check

CABINET SEAL CHECK:

DOORS LOCKED:

D3 Safety Check

CYCLE TIME:

DOSE VERIFICATION:

D4 UVC dose verified?

RESPONSIBLE:

D8 Load and transport for pickup

D7 Add tally, label container

DISINFECTANT SOLUTION:

RESPONSIBLE:

D6 Strap decontamination

PREVENT CROSS-CONTAMINATION:

CHANGE GLOVES

OR

2ND REPROCESSING STAFF MEMBER

D5 Unload masks from rack

BEFORE CLINICAL SHIFT: MASK PICK UP

RESPONSIBLE/ DECON SOLUTION:

E1 Mask retrieved, sanitize container

LOGGED OUT BY:

E2 Log out mask

E3 Don mask/perform seal check

E4 Hand hygiene and start shift

REPROCESSING STAFF SHIFT ENDS

G1 Staff handover

G2 Doff PPE

G3 Hand hygiene and end of shift